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New results on the mass/cost-optimization analysis of a planetary sunshade system

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to present a study on total mass/cost-optimization of planetary sunshade systems, considering the launch, orbital transfer and final photo-gravitational Sun-Earth L1 halo orbit insertion and motion. The Earth's climate changing is mostly due to the increasing concentration of greenhouse gas in the atmosphere which causes the general rise of the temperatures. To mitigate this, a space-based geo-engineering infrastructure has been previously proposed to reduce the oncoming solar radiance, by setting a 'solar light umbrella' between Sun and Earth. In literature, the mass/cost-optimization of a planetary sunshade system has been so far studied without including the orbital-transfer cost. Existing results show that, based on the dynamics system equilibrium of each satellite of the sunshade system, a relationship governs the minimum mass of the deployed sunshade system, its photo-gravitational L1 position and the desired mean solar radiance reduction. Here, for the first time (to the best knowledge of the authors) the analysis of the mass/cost-optimization of a planetary sunshade is extended to include the orbital transfer cost. The total minimum cost considering also the orbital transfer and orbital insertion cost, move the resulting optimal equilibrium position. Four different type of transfers are considered, which are respectively direct transfer with a spaceship or a solar-sail and a transfer through manifolds and parking orbits with a spaceship or the combination of spaceship and solar-sail. The new results are compared with the existing ones. Furthermore, a preliminary evaluation of the numbers of launches from Earth, is presented. The basic assumptions made in this paper are: 1) all of the system is launched from the Earth's surface, 2) operational or planned reusable heavy rocket-launchers are considered.

Keywords: Astrodynamics, Solar Sail, Planetary Sunshade, Space-based Geoengineering, Trajectory Optimization, Sun–Earth–Moon Transfers

Nomenclature

μ	Three-body gravitational parameter [-]
α	Solar Sail Cone Angle [°]
δ	Solar Sail Clock Angle [°]
\hat{n}	Solar Sail normal unity vector [-]
M	Solar Sail Mass [kg]
β	Solar Sail Lightness parameter [-]
$\frac{\delta Q}{Q}$	Solar Radiance Reduction [-]
d	Distance [km]
C	Total cost Function [T\$]

t	Time [s]
$\Delta \mathbf{V}_0$	Impulsive velocity variation at starting orbit [km/s]
$\Delta \mathbf{V}_f$	Impulsive velocity variation for insertion at final orbit [km/s]
\mathbf{X}	State Vector
SB_{EM-L_1}	Sun–Earth/Moon center of mass L_1
$EM-L_1$	Earth–Moon L_1

1. Introduction

One of the major effects of climate change is the rise in Earth's global mean temperature principally due to an increase of CO₂ in the atmosphere, which con-

sequently reduces the effective emissivity of the atmosphere. To mitigate this, a space-based geoengineering infrastructure has been previously proposed to reduce the oncoming solar radiance by setting a ‘solar-light umbrella’, called planetary sunshade system, between the Sun and Earth. The design of the planetary sunshade system would strongly depend on the mitigation scenario chosen [1], in terms of required reduction of solar radiance.

Various sunshade design strategies have been proposed, mainly considering swarm of solar-sail satellites, capable of active control, which will be assembled to build a single occulting disk [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. Furthermore, other architectures have been proposed utilizing space resources, such as diffuse and passively controlled dust clouds [8] or foil sunshades [9, 10]. An international planetary sunshade open-source development platform has also recently been proposed [11], to implement a sustainable sunshade design based on lunar resources. Then, in [12] it is described three space architectures obtainable by using a swarm of solar-sail satellites, analyzing the astrodynamics and proposing different possible families of photo-gravitational CR3BP Halo L_1 orbits. Finally, in [13] it is presented a top-level comparison between space and in-atmosphere geoengineering approaches, based on critical metrics and detailed system and cost analysis, including sustainability and reversibility, scientific and engineering feasibility, cost, and time of execution. Mostly, the different strategies plan to put the sunshade in a cisterrestrial environment, by modelling the planetary sunshade dynamics as a Circular Restricted Three Body Problem (CR3BP), with Solar Radiation Pressure (SRP), hereafter photo-gravitational CR3BP. Nevertheless, several studies analyzed the pros and cons of having it in Earth Orbit [14, 15].

Notably, the astrodynamics transfer problem of the planetary sunshade system that consists of a swarm of solar-sail satellites, in a large number, has remained unexplored. The main objective of the present paper is to fill that knowledge gap.

By considering a transfer with a spaceship, optimal impulsive maneuver transfers between an Earth Parking Orbit (EPO) and lagrangian points have been extensively studied. In [16], it is reported optimal bi-impulsive transfers from primaries to lagrangian

points in the Sun–Earth CR3BP system. Then, in [17] it is presented multiple transfer opportunities from Earth to Moon in the Sun–Earth/Moon Bi-circular Restricted Four Body Problem (BCR4BP) adopting direct transcription and multiple shooting strategy. Moreover, in [18] it is computed minimum ΔV bi-impulsive transfers from Earth to multi-revolution halo orbits in the Earth–Moon Elliptical Restricted Three Body Problem (ER3BP) using differential evolution algorithms. Finally, in [19] it is coupled invariant manifolds and impulsive maneuvers to obtain low-cost transfers between lagrangian points of different CR3BP systems.

Considering a transfer with solar sail, in [3] it is used the strategy in [20] and direct-methods for a near-minimum time transfer from GEO to photo-gravitational L_1 , using a realistic sail model. Then, in [21] it is used pseudospectral method for minimum-time transfers between halo orbits of different sun planet systems. Finally, in [22] it is used the optimal control theory for minimum-time transfers to synchronus heliocentric orbits.

In particular, the main original contributions of the present paper are: 1) The study of the mass/cost-optimization of a sunshade planetary system including the transfer and insertion cost; 2) A comparative analysis, in terms of fuel consumption and time of flight, for four transfer strategies from Earth to photo-gravitational CR3BP L_1 equilibrium points, using spaceships or solar-sails.

The paper is organized as follows: Sec. 2 introduces the equations of motions, the reference frames and the solar radiation pressure effect; Sec. 3 describes the requirements for the planetary sunshade applications; Sec. 4 presents a comparison of four optimal transfer scenarios; Sec. 5 analyze the effect of orbital transfer and insertion on the planetary sunshade mass/cost optimization; finally Sec. 6 concludes the paper.

2. Translational Equations of Motion

This section presents the reference frames and the translational equations of motion for point masses, including the different modelling hypotheses. In this work, the values of primaries’ masses, relative distances and periods are adopted as per [23].

2.1 CR3BP Model

The CR3BP model describes the motion of a point mass spacecraft m subject to the gravitational accelerations of two primaries m_1 and m_2 considered as point masses. The two primaries are performing circular orbits about their common center of mass and the spacecraft doesn't influence their motion.

In order to obtain the equations of motion, it is useful to consider a barycentric, synodic, and co-rotating Cartesian Coordinate System (CCS), defined as follows. Its origin O_{xyz} is located at the center of mass of the m_1 – m_2 system, which is fixed in an inertial frame; its \hat{x} axis is the straight line joining the m_1 center of mass to the m_2 one; its \hat{z} axis is along the angular momentum vector of the m_1 – m_2 system; finally, its \hat{y} axis completes a right-hand CCS. The primaries center of mass are fixed in this CCS, and located along the \hat{x} axis at the points identified by the x -coordinate value $-\mu$ and $1 - \mu$, respectively. The equations of motion describing the orbital dynamics of a spacecraft in the co-rotating CCS and subject to a perturbation $\mathbf{a} = [a_x, a_y, a_z]$ are (for further details, the reader is referred to [19])

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{x} - 2\dot{y} - \frac{\partial U}{\partial x} &= a_x \\ \ddot{y} + 2\dot{x} - \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} &= a_y \\ \ddot{z} - \frac{\partial U}{\partial z} &= a_z, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where

$$U = \frac{1}{2}(x^2 + y^2) + \frac{\mu_1}{\|\mathbf{r}_{1s}\|} + \frac{\mu_2}{\|\mathbf{r}_{2s}\|}, \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{r} &= [x, y, z], \quad \mathbf{r}_1 = [-\mu_2, 0, 0], \\ \mathbf{r}_2 &= [\mu_1, 0, 0], \quad \mathbf{r}_{1s} = \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_1, \quad \mathbf{r}_{2s} = \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_2 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\mu = \frac{m_2}{m_1 + m_2}, \quad \mu_1 = 1 - \mu, \quad \mu_2 = \mu \quad (4)$$

In this work, we will refer to (1) as a first order time-independent system with state $\mathbf{X} = [x, y, z, \dot{x}, \dot{y}, \dot{z}]$, denominated $\dot{\mathbf{X}}(t) = \mathbf{F}_1(\mathbf{X}(t))$ or $\dot{\mathbf{X}}(t) = \mathbf{F}_2(\mathbf{X}(t))$ for respectively Earth–Moon system and Sun–Earth/Moon center of mass system.

2.2 BCR4BP Model

The BCR4BP model describes the motion of a point mass spacecraft m subject to the gravitational accelerations of three primaries m_1, m_2 and m_3 considered as point masses, with $m_3 \gg m_1, m_2$. m_1 and m_2 are performing circular orbits about their common center of mass. m_1 – m_2 center of mass and m_3 are performing circular orbits about their common center of mass and the spacecraft doesn't influence their motion.

In order to obtain the equations of motion, it is useful to consider the barycentric, synodic, and co-rotating Cartesian Coordinate System (CCS), defined in Sec. 2.1. According to the mission scenario, the co-rotating CCS can be preferably described with m_1 – m_2 or m_3 – m_1/m_2 center of mass rotating system and the equations of motion are made adimensional with their respectively characteristic quantities.

The equations of motion describing the orbital dynamics of a spacecraft in m_1 – m_2 corotating CCS and subject to a perturbation $\mathbf{a} = [a_x, a_y, a_z]$ are (for further details, the reader is referred to [23, 24])

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{x} - 2\dot{y} - \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial x} &= a_x \\ \ddot{y} + 2\dot{x} - \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial y} &= a_y \\ \ddot{z} - \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial z} &= a_z, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where

$$\Gamma = U + \frac{\mu_3}{\|\mathbf{r}_{3s}\|} - \frac{\mu_3}{\rho^3}(\mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{r}_3) \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{r}_3 &= [\rho \cos(\theta), \rho \sin(\theta), 0], \quad \mathbf{r}_{3s} = \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_3, \\ \mu_3 &= \frac{m_3}{m_1 + m_2}, \quad \theta = \omega t + \theta_0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $U, \mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \mu, \mu_1, \mu_2$ are same as (2), (3), (4). ρ is the adimensional semi-major axes of m_3 – m_1 m_2 center of mass circular motion, ω is the adimensional angular velocity of m_3 as seen in the m_1 – m_2 co-rotating CCS and θ_0 is m_3 initial angular phase.

We will refer to (5) as a first order time-dependent system with state $\mathbf{X} = [x, y, z, \dot{x}, \dot{y}, \dot{z}]$, denominated $\dot{\mathbf{X}}(t) = \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{X}(t); t)$ for Sun–Earth–Moon system.

2.3 Photo-gravitational Models

The photo-gravitational models describe the effect of SRP on solar sail satellites. $\mathbf{a} = [a_x, a_y, a_z]$ can be expressed in its dimensional form as in [25] such that the direction is parallel to the solar-sail surface normal $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$

$$\mathbf{a} = \beta \frac{Gm_{sun}}{\|\mathbf{r}_{sun-s}\|^2} (\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{sun-s})^2 \hat{\mathbf{n}}, \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{r}_{sun-s} is the Sun-solar sail position vector, $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{sun-s} = \frac{\mathbf{r}_{sun-s}}{\|\mathbf{r}_{sun-s}\|}$ and β corresponds to the SRP-to-solar gravity ratio, that can be expressed as a function of the solar sail area-to-mass ratio

$$\beta = \sigma^* \frac{A}{M} \quad (9)$$

where $\sigma^* \sim 1535 \mathcal{Q}$ [kg/km²], and \mathcal{Q} depends on the solar sail material, ranging from perfectly reflecting surface with $\mathcal{Q} = 1$ to $\mathcal{Q} = 0$ with specular reflection. In our work, we consider $\mathcal{Q} = 1$ and that the solar sail orientation is expressed with respect to Sun–Earth/Moon center of mass corotating CCS where the cone angle α is defined as the angle between $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$, while δ is the clock angle defined as the angle between $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ projection on $\hat{\mathbf{y}} - \hat{\mathbf{z}}$ plane and $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$. In such a way $\hat{\mathbf{n}} = [\cos(\alpha), \sin(\alpha) \cos(\delta), \sin(\alpha) \sin(\delta)]$. Fig. 1 shows the α and δ definition.

Furthermore, since the SRP is the force produced by the sunlight photons impinging on the surface of the satellite, the condition $\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{sun-s} \geq 0$ must be fulfilled. By defining the angle ϕ between $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_1$ and $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$, this condition is expressed as $\cos(\alpha - \phi) \geq 0$. We stress that this condition imposes limits in the values of α which is restricted in the interval $[0, |90 \operatorname{sgn}(\phi) + \phi|]$ [°] for $|\phi| \leq 90$ [°] and in $[| -90 \operatorname{sgn}(\phi) + \phi|, 180]$ [°] for 90 [°] $\leq |\phi| \leq 180$ [°]. Instead, δ has no restriction, and it can go between $[-180, 180]$ [°].

2.4 Equilibria

It is possible to prove that the photo-gravitational CR3BP model defined in (1) admits equilibria for different values of x, y, z with fixed attitude, i.e., α and δ values. Such equilibrium points are found by solving the vectorial equation:

$$-\nabla U = \mathbf{a}, \quad (10)$$

Figure 1: Illustration of a solar sail satellite orientation parameters respect to Sun–Earth/Moon center of mass corotating CCS: cone angle α and clock angle δ

For the photo-gravitational model, the equilibria are time-independent only if the Sun is one of the primaries. We summarize the procedure described in [25] to find the locations of the equilibria of system (1) with SRP. Because of (8), the previous equation implies $\hat{\mathbf{n}} = -\frac{\nabla U}{\|\nabla U\|}$. By replacing this condition in (10), we obtain either the CR3BP limit solution when $\mathbf{a} = 0$ or the equilibria loci for the photo-gravitational CR3BP defined by:

$$\|\nabla U\|^3 \|\mathbf{r}_1\|^4 - \beta(1 - \mu)(\nabla U \cdot \mathbf{r}_{sun-s})^2 = 0. \quad (11)$$

Then, the condition $-\nabla U \cdot \mathbf{r}_{sun-s} \geq 0$ must be fulfilled (because $\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{sun-s} \geq 0$) and the relative equality corresponds to the boundaries of forbidden regions.

3. Requirements for the planetary sunshade application

One of the crucial challenges of the planetary sunshade is to optimize its space system mass according to its location, in order to accomplish a desired solar radiance reduction. The main constraint is that the sunshade must cast a shadow on Earth. In order to achieve this condition, the sunshade center of mass must be close to the joining line between the Sun center and Earth–Moon system's center of mass. It is

possible to demonstrate that there exists an optimum distance \bar{d} that minimizes the total mass of the system which is independent of solar radiance reduction $\frac{\delta Q}{Q}$ needed. This section summarizes the procedure described in [9] and synthesizes the results obtained in [12].

In particular, the optimal position \bar{d} for the sunshade is the photo-gravitational L_1 for $\alpha = \phi = 0$ [°], since from Eq. (10) the sunshade would be located on \hat{x} with $x = x^*$, $y^* = z^* = 0$ [km] and the shading is maximized since \hat{n} is parallel to \hat{x} . From the equilibrium equation in Eq. (11), it yields a relationship between β and the photo-gravitational L_1 distance from Earth–Moon system's center of mass $d^* = 1 - \mu - x^*$

$$\beta(d^*) = -\frac{(d^* + \mu)^2}{(1 - \mu)}(d^* - \frac{(1 - \mu)}{(d^* + \mu)^2} + \frac{\mu}{(d^* - (1 - \mu))^2}). \quad (12)$$

Moreover, \mathcal{A} is a function of d^* and $\frac{\delta Q}{Q}$, since $\frac{\delta Q}{Q}$ is calculated as the squared ratio between the solid angles of the sunshade and of the Sun, as seen from the Earth–Moon system's center of mass, which gives

$$R(d^*) = R_s \frac{d^*}{d_{sem}} \sqrt{\frac{\delta Q}{Q}}, \quad \mathcal{A}(d^*) = \pi R^2(d^*), \quad (13)$$

with R_s as the Sun Radius and d_{sem} as the distance between Sun center and Earth–Moon system's center of mass. Finally, the sunshade mass M is expressed as

$$g(d^*) = \frac{d^{*2}}{(d^* + \mu)^2(-d^* + \frac{(1-\mu)}{(d^* + \mu)^2} - \frac{\mu}{(d^* - (1-\mu))^2})} \quad (14)$$

$$M(d^*) = \sigma^* \frac{\mathcal{A}(d^*)}{\beta(d^*)} = \lambda g(d^*),$$

where $\lambda = \frac{\sigma^* \pi R_s^2 \frac{\delta Q}{Q} (1-\mu)}{d_{sem}^2}$ is a constant. M tends toward infinity when $\beta \sim 0$, i.e., when the photo-gravitational CR3BP reduces to the pure CR3BP. Then, the \bar{d} is equal to $\bar{d} \sim 2.364e + 06$ [km] ($\sim 8.681e + 5$ [km] farther from L_1 associated to pure CR3BP) and it is independent of $\frac{\delta Q}{Q}$, so as β .

This shows that, for every $\frac{\delta Q}{Q}$, \bar{d} and $\beta(\bar{d})$ of the sail would be the same, while M and R have respectively linear and root dependency.

Fig. 2 shows M , R and β as a function of d^* with color as $\frac{\delta Q}{Q}$ from 0.1 [%] to 4 [%], in the d^* interval $[1.5e + 6; 10e + 6]$ [km], including the curve obtained with $\frac{\delta Q}{Q} = 1.7\%$ and $M(\bar{d})$, $R(\bar{d})$ and $\beta(\bar{d})$ values equal to $M(\bar{d}) \sim 2.847e + 11$ [kg], $R(\bar{d}) \sim 1.436e + 03$ [km], $\beta(\bar{d}) = 0.0349$.

Figure 2: Planetary Sunshade Mass (top), β (middle) and Radius (bottom) as a function of the photo-gravitational L_1 distance d^* from Earth–Moon center of mass with color as solar radiance reduction $\frac{\delta Q}{Q}$. The yellow curve is obtained with $\frac{\delta Q}{Q} = 1.7\%$ and magenta point correspond to the quantities value with \bar{d} .

Indeed, the obtained \bar{d} minimizes M and the solar-sail cost according to the dynamical properties of the system, but, if we consider the overall cost of the system, it has to take into account the planetary sunshade transfer and system engineering limitations, which is highly dependent on the photo-gravitational L_1 position, making the \bar{d} computation more complex. For this purpose it is useful to analyze the dynamical

properties of the system for different value of β in the defined d^* interval. In Fig. 3 we plot the location of the equilibria in the $\hat{x}-\hat{y}$ plane and $z = 0$ [km] for different values of $\beta \in (0, 0.187)$, by showing also the respective α value, in the vicinity of the L_1 point originated at the pure Sun–Earth/Moon system’s center of mass CR3BP which is also the solution for the two limit cases $\beta = 0$ and $\hat{n} \cdot \hat{r}_1 = 0$. The respective δ value is constant, and it is equal to 0 [°] and 180 [°] for $y < 0$ [km] and $y > 0$ [km].

Figure 3: Location of the equilibria in the $\hat{x}-\hat{y}$ plane and $z = 0$ [km] with color as β values (top) and α (bottom). The magenta point is the L_1 point originating in the pure CR3BP with $x \sim 1.480e + 8$ [km].

We note that for smaller value of β , the equilibria are distributed in a close curve (whose one of the extrema is the L_1 point of the pure CR3BP), while for larger value of β , these curves are not anymore close and they are getting closer respectively to the Sun and to the boundaries of the forbidden regions defined in Sec. 2.4. Furthermore, α tends toward 0 [°] and 90

[°] near respectively $y = 0$ [km] and the boundaries of the forbidden regions.

4. Optimal Transfer Scenarios

Following the considerations in Sec. 3, in this section the cost of four different orbital transfers that contribute differently to the total planetary sunshade cost according to the sunshade position is analyzed. The transfer starts from a 200 [km] LEO Earth Parking Orbit (EPO), and it is studied for stopping at final photo-gravitational SB_{EM-L_1} positions with \bar{d} between the range $[1.5, 10]e + 06$ [km]. Once the solar-sail satellites arrive in \bar{d} , there will be a further transfer phase (not analyzed in this work) according to one of the three space system architectures defined in [12], i.e., a single assembled solar sail satellite, a swarm of multiple solar sail satellites or in an equilibrium condition either orbiting along a photo-gravitational halo orbits family. For the transfers analyzed, we define $\Delta \mathbf{V}_0 = [\Delta \dot{x}, \Delta \dot{y}, \Delta \dot{z}]_{PO}$, where PO is the initial periodic orbit. The, we introduce $\Delta \mathbf{V}_f = \mathbf{X}_{[4:6]}^T - \mathbf{X}_{[4:6]}(t_f)$ where $\mathbf{X}_{[4:6]}^T$ is the desired final insertion velocity. The transfer cost function to be minimized is the sum of modules of $\Delta \mathbf{V}_0$ and $\Delta \mathbf{V}_f$.

4.1 Bi-Impulsive direct injection from LEO to SB_{EM-L_1}

In this subsection, minimum ΔV bi-impulsive direct transfers are obtained in the Sun-Earth-Moon BCR4BP. The problem reduces to a two point boundary value problem where the optimization variables are the angular position in the EPO of the spacecraft at departure date ϵ , the phasing between Earth-Moon systems and Sun at departure date θ_0 , final time t_f , and $\Delta \mathbf{V}_0$. The optimization problem can be stated as follows

Bi-Impulsive Direct Injection (BCR4BP) Problem

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\epsilon, \theta_0, \Delta \mathbf{V}_0} (\|\Delta \mathbf{V}_0\| + \|\Delta \mathbf{V}_f\|) \\ & \text{subject to} \\ & \dot{\mathbf{X}}(t) = \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{X}(t); t) \quad \forall t \in [0, t_f] \\ & \mathbf{X}(t_0) = \mathbf{X}_{EPO}(\epsilon) + [0, 0, 0, \Delta \mathbf{V}_0], \quad d^*(t_f) = \bar{d}, \\ & 0 \leq \epsilon \leq 2\pi, \quad 0 \leq \theta_0 \leq 2\pi, \quad t_f \leq t_{f, max} \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbf{X}_{EPO}(\epsilon)$ represents the state at the departure date in the EPO at the point specified by ϵ . Multiple instances of the optimization problem have been solved by the *Matlab* function *fmincon* adopting the *sqp-legacy*. $t_{f,max}$ has been set to 365 [days]. Fig. 4 reports all the trajectories as seen in the Sun–Earth/Moon center of mass co-rotating frame. Fig. 5 plots the total ΔV , time of flight optimal values as function of \bar{d} .

Figure 4: Transfers from EPO to multiple SB_{EM-L_1} values, with color as total ΔV required

Figure 5: $\|\Delta \mathbf{v}\|$ required respect to \bar{d} , with color as time-of-flight

The optimal increment in velocity ranges from 3.60 to 7.50 [km/s] while the optimal time of flight from 220 to 365 [days]. It is shown that reaching periodic orbits closer to Earth requires a minor cost in terms of both fuel and time.

4.2 Manifolds and parking orbits approach

A possible transfer scenario consists in a three-stage maneuver composed by:

- Bi-impulsive maneuver from LEO to $EM-L_1$

Table 1: Lyapunov Orbits Parameters

L_1 Point	\mathbf{X}_0 [-]	T_{PO} [-]
SB_{EM-L_1}	[0.9880, 0, 0, 0, 0.0172, 0]	3.252
$EM-L_1$	[0.8767, 0, 0, 0, -0.2704, 0]	2.908

- From $EM-L_1$ to SB_{EM-L_1} by Invariant Manifolds approach
- Bi-impulsive maneuver from SB_{EM-L_1} to photo-gravitational SB_{EM-L_1}

This approach is particularly useful to satisfy operational constraints such as spacecrafts refueling and Earth-spacecraft communication delay. Periodic orbits around $EM-L_1$ and SB_{EM-L_1} assume the role of periodic parking orbits, which can be exploited to deploy the system before departure to final location. In this work, two Lyapunov periodic orbits around $EM-L_1$ and SB_{EM-L_1} have been chosen such that their energies are similar in order to minimize the transfer cost from one to another. The initial state vector \mathbf{X}_0 and period T_{PO} defining the chosen Lyapunov Parking Orbits (LPO) described in the co-rotating CCS are reported in Table. 1. A more accurate choice is out of the scope of this work and can be the subject of further investigations.

4.2.1 Bi-impulsive transfer from LEO to $EM-L_1$

The methodology to quantify maneuver cost for this phase takes inspiration from [18]. Given a circular EPO of 200 km altitude and the target $EM-L_1$ periodic orbit, the optimal bi-impulsive maneuver is found by solving the following problem

Bi-Impulsive back propagation Problem

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\nu, \Delta \mathbf{V}_0} (\|\Delta \mathbf{V}_0\| + \|\Delta \mathbf{V}_f\|) \\ & \text{subject to} \\ & \dot{\mathbf{X}}(t) = \mathbf{F}_1(\mathbf{X}(t)) \quad \forall t \in [0, -t_f] \\ & \mathbf{X}(t_0) = \mathbf{X}_{LPO}(\nu) + [0, 0, 0, \Delta \mathbf{V}_0] \\ & \|\mathbf{X}_{[1:3]}(-t_f) - [-\mu, 0, 0]\| = R_{EPO}, \quad 0 \leq \nu \leq 1 \end{aligned}$$

where $\nu \in [0, 1]$ is the adimensional time fraction of the periodic orbit and R_{EPO} is the radius of the EPO. The optimization has been solved by the *Mat-*

Table 2: Bi-Impulsive Back Propagation Results

ΔV_0 [km/s]	ΔV_f [km/s]	TOF[days]
0.5212	3.1034	4.2578
0.5142	3.0918	12.49
0.4494	3.0794	37.95
0.3844	3.0791	147.0

lab function ga including mutation, crossover and selection of the best members of the population. All the simulations considered a population of 100 members and were run 10 times each. Different families of solutions can be obtained with this procedure (further details can be found in [18]). These transfer families differ in the number of fly-bys around the Earth and so the time of flight. Four results of the simulation are reported in Table. 2. Figures 6 and 7 plot the first and last case with color as velocity. It is visible that a small amount of fuel can be saved at the cost of a significantly increase in the transfer time. If the mission budget allows, it is more convenient to adopt the solution without any fly-by around the Earth.

Figure 6: 1st transfer, with color as velocity

4.2.2 From $EM-L_1$ to SB_{EM-L_1}

Transfers between periodic orbits around lagrangian points of different systems (i.e., Earth-Moon and Sun-Earth-Moon) with different energy can be found with the so-called patched three-body approximation [26, 19], which decouples the four-body problem (4BP) into two CR3BP. In this section, the cost of a transfer between two periodic orbits around respectively $EM-L_1$ and SB_{EM-L_1} is found by the patched three-body approximation. The approach consists in

Figure 7: 4th transfer, with color as velocity

propagating the manifold tubes associated with the two periodic orbits in Sun–Earth–CR3BP and Earth–Moon–CR3BP for a given phasing, computing the manifold tubes intersection set at a Poincaré section (patch surface) passing through the Earth–Moon barycenter, computing the minimum- ΔV maneuver to apply at patch surface which satisfies boundary constraints, and using the previous results as first guess to obtain solution in the BCR4BP including the phasing optimization.

The propagation of the manifolds has been computed by the methodology reported in [27]. In Figure 8 the manifolds generated with $\theta_0 = 0$ [rad] are shown. The plot can be interpreted as a shot of the instantaneous manifolds of the two Lyapunov orbits in the Sun-Earth-Moon system. The red lines represent the unstable manifolds while in black the stable ones. The patch surface passing through the Earth-Moon barycenter is also visible.

Figure 8: Sun-Earth-Moon and Earth-Moon systems' manifolds propagation

Fig. 9 shows the intersection set between the man-

ifolds at patch section U_3 defined as

$$U_3 = \{(y, \dot{y}) \mid x = 1 - \mu, y > 0\} \quad (15)$$

Figure 9: U_3 Poincaré Section

Information from Fig. 9 provided us with appropriate boundaries to start an optimization process where the norm of a maneuver in the $x - y$ plane ($\Delta \mathbf{V} = [\dot{x}^+ - \dot{x}^-, \dot{y}^+ - \dot{y}^-]$) applied at patch surface, such that a forward and back propagation of the states $[x, y, \dot{x}^+, \dot{y}^+]$ and $[x, y, \dot{x}^-, \dot{y}^-]$ asymptotically converge to respectively the selected Lyapunov orbits, is minimized. Finally, Fig. 10 reports the minimum ΔV optimal trajectory in the BCR4BP, with color as velocity. The LPOs are reported in blue. The spacecraft is transferred in 149.4 [days] and a maneuver of 0.265 [km/s] is required.

Figure 10: BCR4BP transfer from $EM-L_1$ to SB_{EM-L_1} LPOs, with color as velocity

4.2.3 From SB_{EM-L_1} to Photo-gravitational SB_{EM-L_1}

In this subsection, minimum ΔV bi-impulsive transfers from the Lyapunov orbit around SB_{EM-L_1} to

the photo-gravitational SB_{EM-L_1} are obtained in the Sun–Earth/Moon center of mass CR3BP.

Similarly to Subsection. 4.2.1, the optimization variables are the scalar ν and $\Delta \mathbf{V}_0$. The two boundary value problem is defined as follows

Bi-Impulsive forward propagation Problem

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\nu, \Delta \mathbf{V}_0} (\|\Delta \mathbf{V}_0\| + \|\Delta \mathbf{V}_f\|) \\ & \text{subject to} \\ & \dot{\mathbf{X}}(t) = \mathbf{F}_2(\mathbf{X}(t)) \quad \forall t \in [0, t_f] \\ & \mathbf{X}(t_0) = \mathbf{X}_{LPO}(\nu) + [0, 0, 0, \Delta \mathbf{V}_0], \quad d^*(t_f) = \bar{d}, \\ & 0 \leq \nu \leq 1, \quad t_f \leq t_{f,max} \end{aligned}$$

The optimization has been solved by the *Matlab* function *fmincon* adopting the *sqp-legacy* algorithm. Multiple simulations have been run to target the same periodic orbits as in Subsection. 4.1. The time of flight has been constrained to be less than 87 days. Fig. 11 reports the trajectories obtained while Fig. 12 plots the total ΔV and the time of flight optimal values as function of \bar{d} . The cost varies from about 0.405 [km/s] for the closest targets to 4.50 [km/s] for the furthest while the time of flight ranges from 72 [days] to the maximum allowed 87 [days].

Figure 11: Transfers from Sun–Earth/Moon center of mass L_1 Lyapunov orbit to multiple SB_{EM-L_1} values

4.3 Solar radiation pressure minimum-time optimal control

In this subsection, minimum ΔV for minimum time bi-impulsive transfers are obtained in the Sun–

Figure 12: $\|\Delta\mathbf{V}\|$ required respect to \bar{d} , with color as time-of-flight

Earth/Moon center of mass BCR4BP via optimal control theory [28] by exploiting SRP.

The minimum-time cost function J to be maximized is expressed as $J = -t_f$, since when the transfer time is minimum, J is maximized. By introducing the function $K(t) = \int_0^t (-1)dt$, then $\dot{K}(t) = -1$, $J = K(t_f)$ and the Hamiltonian H become

$$H = \mathbf{P}\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t)^T, \quad (16)$$

where $\mathbf{P} = [P_x, P_y, P_z, P_{\dot{x}}, P_{\dot{y}}, P_{\dot{z}}, P_K]$ is the differential lagrangian multipliers, thereafter called co-state, and $\mathbf{x}(t) = [\mathbf{X}(t), K(t)]$ is the augmented state. The Eulero-Lagrange equation are given by

$$\dot{\mathbf{P}} = -\frac{\partial H}{\partial \mathbf{x}}, \quad \frac{\partial H}{\partial \alpha} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial H}{\partial \delta} = 0, \quad (17)$$

giving $\dot{P}_K(t) = 0$ and that it is possible to calculate the optimal $\alpha(t), \delta(t)$ control law from the last two conditions. By considering a $\hat{x}-\hat{y}$ planar motion with $z(t) = 0$, we get $P_z(t) = 0$, $P_{\dot{z}}(t) = 0$.

By defining $\gamma(t)$ as the angle between Sun-sail direction and \hat{n} from Eq. (17), it is obtained the optimal control law for $\gamma(t)$ by first defining the quantities $c_1(t)$, $c_2(t)$, $c_3(t)$ as

$$\begin{aligned} c_1(t) &= \cos(\phi(t))P_{\dot{x}} + \sin(\phi(t))P_{\dot{y}} \\ c_2(t) &= \cos(\phi(t))P_{\dot{y}} - \sin(\phi(t))P_{\dot{x}} \\ c_3(t) &= \frac{3}{2} \frac{c_1(t)}{c_2(t)}, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

with $\gamma(t)$ equal to

Figure 13: Angles definition for the Solar-sail in the BCR4BP Earth–Moon corotating CCS

$$\begin{cases} \gamma(t) = \arctan\left(\frac{1}{2} \left(-\frac{c_3(t)}{2} - \sqrt{\frac{c_3(t)^2}{4} + 2} \right)\right), \\ \text{for } c_2(t) \neq 0 \\ \gamma(t) = \frac{\pi}{2}, \text{ for } c_2(t) = 0, c_1(t) \geq 0 \\ \gamma(t) = 0, \text{ for } c_2(t) = 0, c_1(t) < 0, \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

and consequently $\alpha(t)$ and $\delta(t)$ control law is calculated introducing

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(t) &= \gamma(t) + \phi(t) - \theta(t) - \pi \\ c_4(t) &= \text{sgn}(\pi - \psi(t)) \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

and then

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha(t) &= c_4(t)(\psi(t) + \pi(c_4(t) - 1)) \\ \delta(t) &= -\frac{\pi}{2}(c_4(t) - 1); \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Fig. 13 shows the geometry with the angles definition. Finally, if initial and final conditions on $\mathbf{X}(t)$ are set, the transversality conditions become

$$\begin{aligned} P_K(t_f) &= \frac{\partial J}{\partial K(t_f)} = \frac{\partial K(t_f)}{\partial K(t_f)} = 1 \\ P_H(t_f) &= -\frac{\partial J}{\partial t_f} = -\frac{\partial K(t_f)}{\partial t_f} = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

In the next subsection it is analyzed the bi-impulsive direct and from SB_{EM-L_1} to photo-gravitational SB_{EM-L_1} injection, with the formulation described respectively in Sec. 4.2.1 and in

4.2.3 but with the application of SRP optimal control law. The optimization problem have been solved by the *Matlab* function *particleswarm* adopting the particle swarm genetic algorithm to calculate optimal $\epsilon/\nu, \theta_0, \|\Delta\mathbf{V}_0\|, t_f$ and $P_x(0), P_y(0), P_{\dot{x}}(0), P_{\dot{y}}(0)$. $t_{f,max}$ is set to 150 [days].

4.3.1 Bi-impulsive direct injection from LEO to SB_{EM-L_1}

Figures. 14 report all the trajectories as seen respectively in the Sun–Earth/Moon CCS. Fig. 15 plots the total ΔV , time of flight optimal values as function of \bar{d} . The optimal increment in velocity range from 4.3 [km/s] to 7.1 [km/s] while the optimal time of flight from 13 [days] to 56 [days]. As might be expected, reaching periodic orbits closer to Earth requires a minor cost in terms of both fuel and time.

Figure 14: Transfers from EPO to multiple photo-gravitational SB_{EM-L_1} values

Figure 15: $\|\Delta\mathbf{V}\|$ required respect to \bar{d} , with color as time-of-flight

4.3.2 Bi-impulsive injection from SB_{EM-L_1} to photo-gravitational L_1

Figures. 16 report all the trajectories as seen respectively in the Sun–Earth/Moon CCS. Fig. 17 plots the

total ΔV , time of flight optimal values as function of the distance from Earth-Moon barycenter.

Figure 16: Transfers from LPO to multiple photo-gravitational SB_{EM-L_1} values

Figure 17: $\|\Delta\mathbf{V}\|$ required respect to \bar{d} , with color as time-of-flight

The optimal increment in velocity ranges from 0.4 [km/s] to 5 [km/s] while the optimal time of flight from 60 [days] to 105 [days]. There is an initial trend until $\bar{d} \sim 3.5e + 6$ [km] where $\Delta V_0 = 0$ [km/s] and it is characterize by higher periods. After this value of \bar{d} , it is required an initial ΔV_0 and the periods are increasing but with lower values with respect to the maximum of the first trend.

5. Global Cost

Previous studies considered to locate the sunshade at a distance d^* where the system mass is minimized. Indeed, if we consider a certain solar-sail production cost C_{ss} expressed as \$ over mass, the same d^* minimizes also the system cost C , since it would have a linear dependency on the mass as

$$C(d^*) = C_{ss}M(d^*) \quad (23)$$

and so the optimal position is calculated by

derivating respect to d^*

$$C'(d^*) = C_{ss}M'(d^*) = 0 \implies M'(d^*) = 0 \quad (24)$$

Nevertheless, in a more complete scenario, the solar-sail production cost is just a piece of the global development cost. Other entries are for example the launcher propellant and production cost, which are highly dependant on the position of the sunshade \bar{d} , since the mass of propellant needed changes according to the transfer and the ΔV needed.

In [13], it is presented a comprehensive and conservative initial engineering and feasibility cost analysis for the launch and deployment of a planetary sunshade system that is summarized as follows. For this analysis, a two-stage orbit launcher, with a tanker for in-orbit refueling, is considered indicative of commercially disclosed super heavy design modules [29]. In particular, the main input drivers are:

- Radiance reduction $\frac{\delta Q}{Q}$
- Reflectivity factor Q
- Lifetime to be fully operative
- Payload, comparable to SpaceX Starship
- Total mass ascent per launch, comparable to SpaceX Starship
- Solar-sail satellite production cost
- Spaceship, booster, and tanker production costs, comparable to SpaceX Starship
- Launch site cost per launch, comparable to SpaceX Starship
- Spaceship, booster and tanker propellant cost, comparable to SpaceX Starship
- Spaceship, booster and tanker maintenance cost
- Reusability of spaceship, booster and tanker, comparable to SpaceX Starship

Other aspects have an important but secondary impact. These are the implementation time, the specific impulse of the rocket engines, the spaceship, booster and tanker fabrication time, the personnel involvement, the maximum daily number of launches per launchpad and the launchpad fabrication and maintenance cost. In this way, the total cost C is expressed as

$$C(d^*) = f(d^*)M(d^*) \quad (25)$$

where $f(d^*)$ is a non linear function which depends on the heavy launcher design. Consequently, the total cost minimum doesn't coincide with the mass one, since

$$\begin{aligned} C'(d^*) &= f'(d^*)M(d^*) + f(d^*)'M(d^*) = 0 \\ &\implies M'(d^*) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

The main factors that contribute to the global cost are respectively the solar-sail production cost, the propellant cost, and the spaceship, booster and tanker production cost. In this section, it is investigated separately the effect on the total cost minimization due to a variation of two of these variables while the last one is constant. The standard values for the heavy launcher design and cost are taken from [13], while the main factors are varied up to 10 times their standard value, which is respectively 500 [\$/kg] for the solar-sail production cost, 168 [\$/kg] for the propellant cost, and 200, 230 and 130 [M\$] for the spaceship, booster and tanker production cost. Figures 18,19,20 shows the difference ΔD between the distance that minimizes respectively the solar-sail cost and the overall cost, given by Eqs. (24), (26). The transfers are enumerated as 1, 2, 3, 4 for the scenarios described in 4.1, 4.2, 4.3.1, 4.3.2.

From the results obtained, the direct transfer with solar-sail satellites presents the minimum overall cost, with a ΔD that varies up to 14000 [km], showing an higher dependency on launcher production cost and propellant cost. Furthermore, on average, the total daily number of launches (spaceships and tankers) are equal to 1691, 1749, 511 and 1715 for respectively the four transfers considered in order. Naturally, for all transfers, the cost is higher when all the three main factors are higher, and the order of magnitude presented is about hundred/thousands of \$ Trillions. This confirms the importance of optimizing the optical properties of the solar-sail through the Q parameter, since the total cost is directly proportional to it. Indeed, if we consider $Q = 0.17$ and the standard solar-sail production cost, the propellant cost, and the spaceship, booster and tanker production cost used in [13], the cost drops to tens of \$ Trillions as in [13].

Moreover ΔD presents its higher variation for respectively a lower solar-sail production cost, an higher propellant cost factor, and an higher launcher

Figure 18: ΔD variation by varying the solar-sail production cost and propellant cost. Top-left is for transfer 1, top-right is for transfer 2, bottom-left is for transfer 3, bottom-right is for transfer 4

Figure 19: ΔD variation by varying the solar-sail production cost and the launcher production cost. Top-left is for transfer 1, top-right is for transfer 2, bottom-left is for transfer 3, bottom-right is for transfer 4

Figure 20: ΔD variation by varying the launcher production cost and propellant cost. Top-left is for transfer 1, top-right is for transfer 2, bottom-left is for transfer 3, bottom-right is for transfer 4

production cost. This can clearly be explained since the effect of different propellant mass, or equivalently ΔV , is much more pronounced when the propellant cost has a higher importance respect to the solar sail production cost. Then, since the number of tankers for in-orbit refueling directly depends on the total propellant mass, the ΔD variation is more important when the launcher (in this case specifically the tanker) production cost is higher. These results show that the direct transfer with solar-sail satellites has the better performances. Furthermore, Fig. 15 shows that this transfer scenario has also the lowest time of flight, due to minimum-time optimal control law adopted. Anyway, several aspects need to be studied more to assert that this would be the best technical solution. Indeed, the direct transfer with solar-sail satellites implies an higher number of both transfers and consequently operations of in-orbit refueling. Therefore, the transfer mission scenario optimization would be more challenging. Nevertheless, these results provide important hints that had to be considered when the total swarm transfer is optimized.

6. Conclusions

This paper introduced a new analysis of the mass/cost-optimization of a sunshade planetary system for Earth's climate change mitigation. The transfer and insertion cost of the solar sails from Earth to photo-gravitational Sun–Earth/Moon center of mass L_1 is fully studied. It has been considered both transfers with spaceships and solar sails. Fuel consumption and time of flight has been compared for the transfer missions. The main factors that drive the overall cost are individuated and sensitivity analysis are performed, quantifying the transfer effect on the planetary sunshade final position. Direct injection with solar-sail shows promising results in terms of minimum ΔV , time of flight and overall cost, with the cons of an higher number of transfers and in-orbit refueling operations.

The newly found results might be of both theoretical and practical interest, as they treat, for the first time to the best knowledge of the authors, the astrodynamics of a transfer of swarm of solar-sail satellites in the photo-gravitational Sun–Earth/Moon center of mass L_1 equilibrium point.

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